

Project Deliverable

Project Number: 325275	Project Acronym: SAPPHIRE	Project Title: System Automation of PEMFCs with Prognostics and Health management for Improved Reliability and Economy
Instrument: Collaborative Project (CP)		Thematic Priority FUEL CELL AND HYDROGEN JOINT UNDERTAKING
Title: <h3 style="text-align: center;">Website</h3>		
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Organisation notes:		

Dissemination level (Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme)		
PU	Public	<h1>PU</h1> Public
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)	
RE	Restricted to a group defined by the consortium (including the Commission)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	

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Abstract :

EIFER developed an information platform (website) dedicated to the project to ensure dissemination to the Internet community. For this purpose, a domain name was purchased (<http://www.sapphire-project.eu/>). The website offers some information about project objectives, content and partners and is continuously updated to share status of advancement and public results with the scientific community.

Keywords :

Website, internet, dissemination

Revision History

Rev.	Date	Description	Author (Organisation)
1	Nov 21, 2013	First version of the report	A. Esposito (EIFER)

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1. SAPPHIRE WEBSITE

EIFER developed an informatics platform (website) dedicated to the project to ensure dissemination to the internet community. For this purpose, the following domain name was purchased:

<http://www.sapphire-project.eu/>

Homepage

Figure 1 – SAPHIRE website homepage

Figure 1 shows the website homepage with the project logo and title. From this page, it is possible to access the other pages.

About

A screenshot of the page *about* is illustrated in Figure 2, where general information about the project objectives, budget and content is provided.

Figure 2 – SAPHIRE website about

Partners

The *partners* list along with hyperlinks to their respective website is provided on the page *partners* as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – SAPHIRE website *partners*

Map

Figure 4 shows the location (*map*) of the several partners on the Europe map.

Figure 4 – SAPHIRE website *map*

People

The list of project participants for each partner, along with the WP leaders, is provided on the page *people* (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – SAPHIRE website *people*

Login

The website offers also the possibility of logging in for the administration and the other partners to upload material and information to catalyse dissemination (Figure 6).

Figure 6 – SAPHIRE website *login*